

Dibenzonaphthrones and Related Compounds

J. N. Chatterjea and N. Prasad

New syntheses of dibenzonaphthyrone have been carried out from (i) 2,2-dimethoxysuccinonitrile and *trans* 2,2-dimethoxydicyanostilbene. Several derivatives of dibenzonaphthyrone have been synthesised from 3-(2'-methoxyphenyl)-4-ethoxycarbonylcoumarins prepared by the method of Borsche and Wannagat³. The structures have been confirmed by independent conventional syntheses. Borsche and Wannagat's synthesis of 3-phenylcoumarin-4-carboxylic acid has been extended and it is shown that if α -acetylphenylacetonitrile be employed in place of ethyl phenylcyanopyruvate, good yields of 3-phenyl-4-methylcoumarins are obtained.

During our researches on the structural determination¹ and synthesis² of 1'-oxo-(2':3'-4:3) indenocoumarin, we took opportunity to study an extension of Borsche and Wannagat's synthesis³ of 3-phenylcoumarin-4-carboxylic acid in order to apply the method to the synthesis of dibenzonaphthyrone (type II—VI) which have not been studied in much detail⁴ in contrast to extensively studied naturally occurring ellagic acid and derivatives which have superficially analogous structures⁵.

Resorcinol on condensation with ethyl *o*-methoxyphenyl-cyanopyruvate gave the coumarin (I) by an adaptation of Borsche and Wannagat's method. This on treatment

- II, R=OH, R'=H
 III, R=OMe, R'=H
 IV, R=R'=OH
 V, R=OH, R'=Me
 VI, R=R'=H

1. Chatterjea, Prasad and Banerjee, *This Journal*, 1964, **41**, 93.
2. Chatterjea, Gupta and Prasad, *Chem. Ber.*, 1966, **99**, 2699.
3. Borsche and Wannagat, *Annalen*, 1950, **589**, 81.
4. Chovin, *Compt. rend.*, 1941, **212**, 549; *ibid*, 1942, **215**, 466; *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1944, **11**, 82; *Chem. Abs.*, 1945, **39**, 932; Chatterjea, *This Journal*, 1959, **36**, 71.
5. Dean, "Naturally Occurring Oxygen Ring Compounds", Butterworths (1963), p. 211.

with pyridine hydrochloride gave the hydroxydibenzonaphthyrone(II) which was methylated to (III). In a similar manner the naphthyrone (IV), (V) and (VII) were prepared from phloroglucinol, orcinol and 1-naphthol. The structures of these products were

confirmed by an alternative synthesis developed earlier by Chovin⁴. Thus, the *iso*-oxindigo (VIII) prepared by the condensation of either coumarandione and 6-methoxy*iso*-coumaranone or 6-methoxycoumarandione with *isocoumaranone* was isomerised to(III) by successive treatments with alkali and acid. Similarly other dibenzonaphthyrone prepared by the first route were also secured from the related *iso*-oxindigos (*vide* experimental).

A different synthesis of dibenzonaphthyrone (VI) was effected from 2,2-dimethoxyphenylsuccinonitrile (IX) which was prepared by the method of Davis⁶ by the condensation of *o*-methoxybenzaldehyde with *o*-methoxybenzyl cyanide in the presence of sodium cyanide. The compound exists in two polymorphic forms, m.p. 110° and 191°, the lower melting form can be transformed to the higher melting form by seeding a solution of the former with the latter. On treatment with pyridine hydrochloride (IX) gave a mixture of (VI) and its dihydro-derivative (X) separable by chromatography. It may be noted that (X) can exist in *cis*—and *trans* forms. The *meso* form of (IX) would give rise to the *trans* variety and the racemic form of (IX) would afford the *cis* variety. Since catalytic hydrogenation of (VI) is likely to give the *cis* isomer which is already known⁴, the present isomer which has a different melting point may be assigned the *trans* structure.

A more effective synthesis of (VI) was carried out from 2,2-dimethoxydicyanostilbene (XI) and pyridine hydrochloride. The stilbene (XI) was prepared from *o*-methoxymandelonitrile which was converted into *o*-methoxy- α -chlorobenzylcyanide by thionyl chloride and thence dimerised to (XI) by alcoholic ammonia according to a known procedure⁷. An alternative exploratory route was attempted from *trans* 2,2-dimethoxystilbene (XII) which was prepared from 2,2-dimethoxybenzoin through the desyl chloride

6. J. Davis, *Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 1752.

7. Michael and Jeanpretre, *Ber.*, 1892, **25**, 1680; v. Braun, *ibid*, 1903, **36**, 2652. Liquid ammonia or alcoholic ammonia is more effective than sodium alkoxides (Private Communications from Prof. A. R. Kidwai).

(XIV) by treatment with zinc dust in acetic acid solution according to a standard procedure⁸. But experiments on the metalation of this stilbene so as to obtain the dicarboxylic acid (XIII) on carbonation, were not very fruitful.

XI, R=CN

XII, R=H

XIII, R=COOH

XIV

Both *iso*-oxindigo and dibenzonaphthyrone gave colourless *leuco* compounds on reduction with zinc dust in acetic acid. These proved difficult to purify. Both dissolved in alkali and the alkaline solution on acidification gave dibenzonaphthyrone by rapid oxidation.

It may be added that by an extension of Borsche coumarin synthesis, α -acetylphenylacetonitrile was condensed with resorcinol, 1- and 2-naphthol to give 3-phenyl-4-methyl-7-hydroxycoumarin, 3-phenyl-4-methyl-7:8-benzocoumarin and 3-phenyl-4-methyl-5:6-benzocoumarin respectively.

EXPERIMENTAL

All m.p.s. are uncorrected. The u.v. and i.r. spectra were determined in Perkin Elmer Spectrophotometers (Models 137 both). The extinction coefficients of u.v. spectra were not determined.

6-Methoxyiso-oxindigo. Method (a). 6-Methoxy-coumarandione (0.5 g.) was dissolved in diethylene glycol (5 ml) and treated with hydrazine hydrate (0.2 c.c.) 100%. The mixture became warm and the solution heated on the water bath for half hour and then treated with potassium hydroxide (0.2 g.) and the temperature raised to 200° for 2 hours. The mixture was cooled, diluted with water, acidified and repeatedly extracted with small quantities of ether (5×5 ml). On removal of solvent, 2-hydroxy-4-methoxyphenylacetic acid (0.4 g., m.p. 131° on crystallisation from chloroform) was obtained. The acid distilled at 180°/16 m.m. yielding 6-methoxyisocoumaranone as a colourless liquid which solidified on cooling, m.p. 55°.

An equimolecular mixture of coumarandione (0.74 g.) and 6-methoxyisocoumaranone (0.82 g.) was treated with a slight excess of phosphorus tribromide (1.0 ml.) and the mixture heated on the water bath with the exclusion of moisture for half hour. The mixture turned deep brown and solidified. Excess of phosphorous tribromide was decomposed carefully by the addition of crushed ice. The yellowish brown crystalline 6-methoxyiso-oxindigo was collected. This crystallised from acetic acid as brownish orange needles, m.p. 219°; yield, 0.6 g.

⁸ Fieser, "Experiments in Organic Chemistry", Heath & Co, Second Edition, p. 178.

(b) To the mixture of 6-methoxycoumarandione (0.9 g.) and *isocoumarone* (0.7 g.) was added phosphorus tribromide (1.2 ml.) and the mixture heated on water bath for thirty minutes. The mixture was cooled and poured into crushed ice. The crystals of 6-methoxy*iso-oxindigo* (0.55 g.) was collected and crystallised from acetic acid in needles, m.p. and mixed m.p. 219°. (Found: C, 69.10; H, 3.20. $C_{17}H_{10}O_5$ requires C, 69.38; H, 3.30%). ($\lambda_{\max}^{\text{alc}}$ 206 m μ and 260 m μ . Carbonyl absorption at 5.62 μ).

7. *Methoxycoumarino* (3:4-4':3') *coumarin*:

Method (a): Isomerisation of 6-methoxyiso-oxindigo: The above mentioned 6-methoxy-*iso-oxindigo* (0.5 g) was treated with sodium hydroxide solution (10%) and heated on water bath for five to ten minutes. The solution was filtered and the pale yellow solution was acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid when a yellow crystalline mass was precipitated in quantitative yield. This was collected and crystallised from acetic acid to give the dibenzonaphthyrone in fine yellow wooly needles, m.p. 261°. The compound gave fluorescence in acetic acid solution. (Found: C, 69.2; H, 3.3. $C_{17}H_{10}O_5$ requires C, 69.5; H, 3.4%). ($\lambda_{\max}^{\text{alc}}$ 210 m μ . Carbonyl absorption at 5.80 μ).

Method (b): 3-(2'-Methoxyphenyl)-4-ethoxycarbonyl-7-hydroxycoumarin: Resorcinol (1.1 g.) and ethyl *o*-methoxyphenylcyanopyruvate (2.47 g.) were dissolved in dry acetic acid (70 ml.) and the solution was saturated with dry hydrogen chloride at room temperature (about three hours). Freshly fused zinc chloride was then added and the stream of dry hydrogen chloride was continued for two hours more at 50°. After twelve hours, the yellow solution was diluted with water to about one litre. The yellow flocculent mass of the *coumarin* was collected and crystallised from dilute alcohol in yellow plates, m.p. 185.86°; yield, 1.05 g. (Found: C, 66.9; H, 4.8. $C_{19}H_{16}O_6$ requires C, 67.0; H, 4.7%).

7. *Hydroxycoumarino* (3:4-4':3') *coumarin*: The aforesaid *coumarin* (0.3 g.) was mixed with pyridine hydrochloride (6.0 g.) and heated in an oil bath at 200-10° in an atmosphere of carbon dioxide for two hours with the exclusion of moisture. The melt was cooled, treated with dilute hydrochloric acid and heated on water bath for one hour. Next day the dirty yellow crystalline precipitate was collected and crystallised from pyridine in orange yellow needles which melted and decomposed at about 295°; yield 0.26 g. The compound was readily soluble in dilute sodium hydroxide (1%) and insoluble in sodium bicarbonate solution. (Found: C, 68.6; H, 3.0. $C_{16}H_8O_5$ requires C, 68.5; H, 2.8%). The compound (0.19 g.) was dissolved in acetone (25 ml.) and then refluxed with anhydrous potassium carbonate (2.0 g.) and methyl iodide (1.5 ml) for six hours. The yellow acetone solution was filtered and the solvent removed by distillation. The residue was treated with alcohol and the yellow crystals of 7-methoxycoumarino (3:4-4':3') *coumarin* was collected. This crystallised either from acetic acid or pyridine in bright yellow wooly needles, m.p. 261°. The m.p. was not depressed when mixed with the sample prepared by method (a). The compound exhibited strong fluorescence in pyridine and acetic acid.

6:6'-*Dimethoxyiso-oxindigo*: 6-Methoxycoumarandione (0.89 g.) and 2-hydroxy-4-methoxyphenylacetic acid (0.91 g.) [or 6-methoxyisocoumaranone (0.82 g.)] were mixed intimately and treated with phosphorus tribromide (1.0 c.c.) The colour of the mixture turned to bottle green. This was heated on water bath for twenty minutes. Brisk evolution of hydrobromic acid gas took place and the colour of the mixture changed to dark red. The cooled mixture was treated with crushed ice. The *iso-oxindigo* separated as

gummy mass which crystallised from acetic acid in dark red needles, m.p. 305°; yield, 0.4 g. (Found: C, 67; H, 3.8. $C_{18}H_{12}O_6$ requires C, 66.6; H, 3.7%) ($\lambda_{\max}^{\text{alc}}$ 205, 245 (shoulder), 274 μ . Carbonyl absorption at 5.65 μ).

7-Methoxycoumarino (3:4-4':3')-7-methoxycoumarin: The above *iso-oxindigo* (0.2 g.) was dissolved in sodium hydroxide solution (15 cc., 10%) by warming on water bath (about 20 minutes). The clear solution obtained after filtration was acidified with hydrochloric acid to congo red. The coumarin (0.15 g.) was collected and crystallised from pyridine in light orange wooly needles, m.p. above 310°. The compound exhibited a strong fluorescence in acetic acid and in pyridine. (Found: C, 66.5; H, 3.7. $C_{18}H_{12}O_6$ requires C, 66.6; H, 3.7%). ($\lambda_{\max}^{\text{alc}}$ 208 and 260 μ . Carbonyl absorption at 5.80 μ).

5:7-Dihydroxycoumarino (3:4-4':3') coumarin.

Method (a): 4:6-Dihydroxyiso-oxindigo: 2:4:6-Trihydroxyphenylglyoxalic acid (1.98 g.) was mixed intimately with 2-hydroxyphenylacetic acid (1.52 g.) and to this mixture phosphorus tribromide (2.0 ml.) was added and heated on water bath for half an hour. On working up in the usual manner the *iso-oxindigo* (0.7 g.) was obtained which on repeated crystallisation from acetic acid was obtained in dark red needles, m.p. 305°. (Found: C, 65.2; H, 2.7. $C_{16}H_8O_6$ requires C, 64.9; H, 2.7%). ($\lambda_{\max}^{\text{alc}}$ 207 and 255 μ . Carbonyl absorption at 5.61 μ).

Isomerisation: The above *iso-oxindigo* (0.5 g.) was dissolved in sodium hydroxide (15 ml, 10%), by warming on water bath for twenty minutes. This was filtered and the clear solution was acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid. The *coumarin* (0.4 g.) was collected and crystallised from acetic acid in red prismatic needles, m.p. 303°.

Method (b): 3-(2'-Methoxyphenyl)-4-ethoxycarbonyl-5:7-dihydroxycoumarin: Phloroglucinol (0.81 g.) and ethyl *o*-methoxy-phenyleyanophyruvate were dissolved in dry acetic acid (25 ml.) and the clear solution was saturated with dry hydrochloric acid gas at room temperature (about two hours). Anhydrous zinc chloride (1.0 g.) was then added and the passing of hydrochloric acid gas was continued for two hours more keeping the temperature of bath at 50-60°. The colour of the solution turned to deep yellow and the shining crystals of ketimine hydrochloride separated. After five to six hours the mixture was diluted 400 ml. with water. The flocculent precipitate was collected after twelve hours. The coumarin crystallised from dilute methanol in cream coloured needles, m.p. 295°; yield 0.55 g. (Found: C, 62.2; H, 4.7. $C_{19}H_{16}O_7$ requires C, 61.9; H, 4.8%).

The above mentioned coumarin (0.2 g.) was heated with pyridine hydrochloride (2.0 g.) at 200-10° for two hours in an atmosphere of carbon dioxide with the exclusion of moisture. The melt was cooled and heated with dilute hydrochloric acid on water bath for half an hour. On crystallisation from acetic acid 5:7-dihydroxycoumarino (3:4-4':3') coumarin was obtained as red prismatic needles, m.p. and mixed m.p. 303°; yield 0.15 g. (Found: C, 65.0; H, 2.7. $C_{16}H_8O_6$ requires C, 64.9; H, 2.7%). ($\lambda_{\max}^{\text{alc}}$ 211, 263 and 345 μ . Carbonyl absorption at 5.81 μ).

5:7-Dimethoxycoumarino (3:4-4':3') coumarin: To the suspension of the dihydroxycoumarin in ether, ethereal diazomethane was added. Brisk evolution of nitrogen took place. After twelve hours the ether was evaporated and the orange residue of methylated product was crystallised repeatedly from acetic acid and obtained as

orange needles, m.p. 240°. (Found: C, 67.0; H, 3.5. $C_{18}H_{12}O_6$ requires C, 66.6; H, 3.7%).

3-(2'-Methoxyphenyl) 4-ethoxycarbonyl-5-methyl-7-hydroxy-coumarin: Orcinol (0.71 g.) and ethyl *o*-methoxy-phenyloxyacrylate (1.2 g.) were dissolved in acetic acid (25 ml.) and the solution was saturated with dry hydrochloric acid gas. Anhydrous zinc chloride (1.0 g.) was then added and the mixture saturated with hydrochloric acid gas for further two hours at 50-60°. On working up in the usual manner a low melting substance was obtained which contained nitrogen and gave ammonia when boiled with sodium hydroxide solution (10%). This low melting solid was hydrolysed with dilute hydrochloric acid on water bath for four hours. The coumarin (0.5 g.) was collected and crystallised from dilute methanol in needles, m.p. 220°. (Found: C, 67.5; H, 5.0. $C_{20}H_{18}O_6$ requires C, 67.8; H, 6.1%).

5-Methyl-7-hydroxycoumarino(3:4-4':3') coumarin: The foregoing coumarin (0.25 g.) was heated with pyridine hydrochloride (2.5 g.) at 200-10° for two hours in an atmosphere of nitrogen with the exclusion of moisture. The brown melt was cooled and heated with dilute hydrochloric acid on water bath for half an hour. The coumarin separated as dirty brown mass was collected and crystallised from acetic acid in beautiful dark red needles, m.p. 263-64°. (Found: C, 69.1; H, 3.3. $C_{17}H_{10}O_5$ requires C, 69.3; H, 3.4%). ($\lambda_{\max}^{\text{alc}}$ 210, 258 and 315 μ . Carbonyl absorption at 5.80 μ).

4:5-Benzoisoxindigo: Method (a): 2-Hydroxy-1-naphthalene acetic acid (1.01 g.) was mixed thoroughly with coumarandione (0.74 g.) and to the mixture phosphorus tribromide (1.0 cc.) was added. After the vigorous reaction was over, the mixture was heated on water bath for half an hour and worked up in the usual manner. The isoxindigo was obtained as brown crystals in very poor yield (80 mg.). This crystallised from acetic acid in golden yellow needles, m.p. 269-70°. The compound gave a deep orange colour with concentrated sulphuric acid. When 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalene acetic acid was replaced with its lactone, the yield was still poorer. (Found: C, 76.2; H, 3.2. $C_{20}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 76.4; H, 3.1%). ($\lambda_{\max}^{\text{alc}}$ 206 and 255 μ . Carbonyl absorption at 5.66 μ).

Method (b): A mixture of 4:5-benzoisocoumarandione (0.5 g.), coumarandione (0.37 g.), hydrobromic acid (1.0 ml., 48%) and acetic acid was refluxed. After half an hour, golden yellow needles began to separate. The refluxing was continued for an hour more, cooled and the isoxindigo (0.1 g.) was collected. This was crystallised from acetic acid in needles, m.p. 269-70°.

5:6-Benzocoumarino (3:4-4':3') coumarin: The isoxindigo (0.13 g.) was treated with sodium hydroxide solution (10 cc., 10%) and warmed on water bath (20 minutes). After filtration the clear solution acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid. The yellow precipitate (0.1 g.) was collected. The coumarin crystallised from acetic acid in yellow wooly needles, m.p. 259°. The compound gave red colour with concentrated sulphuric acid. (Found: C, 76.5; H, 3.0. $C_{20}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 76.4; H, 3.1%). ($\lambda_{\max}^{\text{alc}}$ 217, 238 and 291 μ . Carbonyl absorption at 5.81 μ).

7:8-Benzocoumarino (3:4-4':3') coumarin: 6:7-Benzoisoxindigo: A mixture of 6:7-benzocoumarandione (0.5 g.), isocoumarandione (0.37 g.) and phosphorus tribromide

(1.0 ml.) was heated on water bath for half an hour. On working up in the usual manner the *iso-oxindigo* (0.2 g.) was obtained which crystallised from acetic acid in orange needles, m.p. 279°. (Found: C, 76.2; H, 3.3. $C_{20}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 76.4; H, 3.1%). ($\lambda_{\max}^{\text{alc}}$ 206.5 and 252.5 μ . Carbonyl absorption at 5.66 μ). The *iso-oxindigo* was isomerised in quantitative yield by warming with dilute sodium hydroxide solution (10%) on water bath for 10 to 20 minutes followed by acidification.

7:8-*Benzocoumarino* (3:4-4':3') *coumarin* crystallised from acetic acid in orange needles, m.p. 258°. (Found: C, 76.0; H, 3.0. $C_{20}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 76.4; H, 3.1%). ($\lambda_{\max}^{\text{alc}}$ 224, 253, 291 (shoulder), 304 (shoulder) and 320 μ . Carbonyl absorption at 5.82 μ).

Alternative preparation:

3-(2'-*Methoxyphenyl*-4-*ethoxycarbonyl*-7-8-*benzocoumarin*: Freshly distilled α -naphthol (1.2 g.) and ethyl *o*-methoxyphenylcyanopyruvate (2.1 g.) were dissolved in dry acetic acid (70 ml.) and saturated with dry hydrogen chloride at room temperature. Anhydrous zinc chloride (1.5 g.) was then added and hydrogen chloride was passed for further two hours keeping the temperature between 50 to 60°. The solution turned dark brown and shining crystals separated. On dilution with water, a dark red gummy mass was obtained which deposited orange coloured prismatic needles on treatment with acetic acid, m.p. 254-55°. (Found: C, 74.0; H, 4.6. $C_{23}H_{18}O_5$ requires C, 73.8; H, 4.8%).

On treatment of above coumarin with pyridine hydrochloride in the usual manner, a dirty yellow mass was obtained in very poor yield, m.p. 224-33°. The compound was further purified by several crystallisations from acetic acid and the product, m.p. 258° gave no depression in melting point when mixed with the sample prepared above.

Reduction of Iso-oxindigo: *Iso-oxindigo* (0.2 g.) was dissolved in acetic acid (5.0 ml.) and then treated with zinc dust (0.5 g.). The colourless solution was filtered and the filtrate was diluted with water. The white precipitate was collected and crystallised from acetic acid in pinkish prisms, m.p. 198-99° with previous sintering at 185°.

This sublimed to yellow needles on heating presumably forming *iso-oxindigo*. (Found: C, 71.3; H, 4.2. $C_{16}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 72.0; H, 3.7%) ($\lambda_{\max}^{\text{alc}}$ 208, 274 and 281 μ . Carbonyl absorption at 5.48 μ).

The above *leuco* compound was dissolved in dilute sodium hydroxide solution (10%) by warming on water bath and filtered. The filtrate on acidification with concentrated hydrochloric acid gave dibenzonaphthyrone in quantitative yield, m.p. and mixed m.p. 300°.

Reduction of Coumarino (3:4-4':3') *coumarin* (*dibenzonaphthyrone*): *Coumarino* (3:4-4':3') *coumarin* (0.2 g.) was reduced with zinc dust in acetic acid and worked up as above. The white flocculent precipitate was collected and crystallised from acetic acid in pinkish prismatic needles, m.p. 235-36° with shrinkage at 229°. On heating it sublimed to yellow needles. (Found: C, 71.2; H, 3.6. $C_{16}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 72.0; H, 3.7%). ($\lambda_{\max}^{\text{alc}}$ 207, 268 and 275 μ . Carbonyl absorption at 5.63 μ).

The compound dissolved in warm sodium hydroxide solution giving a yellow solution which on acidification yielded dibenzonaphthyrone, m.p. and mixed m.p. 300°.

2,2'-Dimethoxydiphenylsuccinonitrile: A solution of sodium cyanide (6.2 g.) in water (10 ml.) was heated on water bath till clear solution was obtained and then pure methanol (40 cc.) was added to it and refluxed. *o*-Methoxy benzylcyanide (6.2 g.) was added and the mixture again refluxed. A solution of *o*-methoxybenzaldehyde (6.0 ml.) and *o*-methoxybenzylcyanide (3.7 g.) in methanol (10 ml.) was added in drops to the refluxing solution with stirring for half an hour. The solution was refluxed for further half an hour and then left in refrigerator overnight. An oil separated which deposited crystals on stirring. The nitrile was collected and washed with aqueous methanol (75%), and then cold ether. The crude compound crystallised from ethanol in colourless prisms, m.p. 110°. On recrystallisation three to four times the m.p. rose to 191°. The sample of m.p. 110° could be transformed completely into the sample m.p. 191° by dissolving in ethanol and seeding with the latter. (Found: N, 7.7; $C_{18}H_{16}O_2$ requires N, 8.0%).

Demethylation: The above nitrile (1.0 g.) was heated with pyridine hydrochloride (5.0 g.) at 200-10° for two hours in an atmosphere of carbon dioxide with the exclusion of moisture. On working up in the usual manner a mixture of yellow and colourless crystals was obtained. The mixture was dissolved in benzene and the solution was passed through an alumina column. The yellow benzene elute which came down first deposited yellow wooly needles of dibenzonaphthyrone which on three crystallisations from acetic acid had m.p. and mixed m.p. 300°.

The alumina column was next eluted with ethanol. On concentration, impure dihydrodibenzonaphthyrone was obtained which after four recrystallisations (charcoal) obtained in prismatic rods, m.p. 209-10°. (Found: C, 73.5; H, 4.1. $C_{16}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 72.2; H, 3.9%) - ($\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{alc}}$ 272 and 325 μ . Carbonyl absorption at 5.89 μ).

2,2-Dimethoxystilbene.—*2,2*-Dimethoxybenzoin (1.0 g.) was heated with excess of thionyl chloride (1.5 ml.) on steambath for ten minutes and the excess of reagent was removed under reduced pressure. The residue was treated with petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°), boiled and removed under reduced pressure. The desyl chloride (XIV), obtained as a pale viscous oil, was dissolved in 95% ethanol and treated with sodium borohydride (100 mg.). After ten minutes the solution was refluxed for an hour with zinc dust (0.5 g.) and acetic acid (1.0 ml). The mixture was cooled and extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was washed twice with an equal volume of water containing a few drops of hydrochloric acid then in turn with sodium carbonate solution (5%) and saturated sodium chloride solution. On drying over anhydrous magnesium sulphate and evaporation of ether solution the crystals of *trans* 2,2-dimethoxystilbene, (0.3 g) were deposited which crystallised from ethanol in prismatic needles, m.p. 136°. The melting point was not depressed when mixed with the authentic sample prepared by the pyrolysis of bis (2-methoxybenzal) hydrazine according to the method of Pascal *et al.*⁹

2,2-Dimethoxydicyanostilbene: *o*-Methoxymandelonitrile (2.0 g.) heated with excess of thionyl chloride for half an hour. On removing the excess of thionyl chloride in usual manner α -chloro-*o*-methoxybenzylcyanide was obtained as brown oil. Excess of methanolic ammonia was poured into it and the mixture left in a refrigerator for a week. No crystals separated. Solvent was removed by distillation and the residue was treated with water. This was then extracted with ether and the ethereal layer was washed repeatedly with dilute hydrochloric acid and then with water, dried ($MgSO_4$) and evaporated to give a

viscous oil which deposited crystals on treatment with ethanol and cooling. 2,2-Dimethoxydicyanostilbene crystallised from ethanol in prismatic rods, m.p. 180-81°. (Found: N, 9.8. $C_{18}H_{14}O_2N_2$ requires N, 9.7%). ($\lambda_{\max}^{alc}$ 207 and 262 $m\mu$).

Dibenzonaphthyrone from 2,2-Dimethoxydicyanostilbene: 2,2-Dimethoxydicyanostilbene (0.1 g.) was heated with pyridine hydrochloride (1.0 g.) in an atmosphere of nitrogen at 210-20° under dry condition for one and half hour. At first a homogeneous melt was obtained which soon deposited yellow needles. This was cooled and heated on water bath for half an hour, with dilute hydrochloric acid. The yellow crystals of coumarino (3:4-4':3') coumarin was collected in quantitative yield and crystallised from acetic acid in wooly needles, m.p. and mixed m.p. 303°.

3-Phenyl-4-methyl-7-hydroxycoumarin.—Resorcinol (2.75 g.) and α -acetylphenylacetonitrile (3.95 g.) was dissolved in dry acetic acid (75 ml.) by warming on water bath slightly. The clear solution was then saturated with dry hydrochloric acid gas at room temperature (about 2 to 3 hours). Freshly fused zinc chloride (2.5 g.) was then added and a stream of dry hydrochloric acid gas was continued for two hours at 50-60°. The colour of solution was turned brown and bright colourless crystals were separated. After twelve hours the mixture was diluted to about 300 cc. and the coumarin (1.85 g.) was collected and crystallised from alcohol in colourless needles, m.p. 226° (lit.¹⁰, m.p. 226°). (Found: C, 76.10; H, 4.70. $C_{16}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 76.19; H, 4.76%).

On heating with acetic anhydride in presence of fused sodium acetate, 3-phenyl-4-methyl-7-acetoxycoumarin was obtained which crystallised from dilute alcohol in colourless needles, m.p. 184-85° (lit., m.p. 185°).

3-Phenyl-4-methyl-7:8-benzocoumarin: Freshly distilled α -naphthol (1.44 g.) and α -acetylphenylacetonitrile (1.59 g.) were dissolved in dry acetic acid (50-60 ml) and the solution was saturated with dry hydrochloric acid gas at room temperature. Freshly fused zinc chloride (1.0 g.) was then added and hydrochloric acid gas was bubbled for two hours more and the mixture left for three weeks. The solution turned brown and deposited a few crystals. This was then diluted to 300 ml. with water and left overnight. 3-Phenyl-4-methyl-7:8-benzocoumarin separated as brownish grey mass which crystallised from alcohol (charcoal) in colourless wooly needles, m.p. 212° (lit.¹¹, m.p. 215-16°; lit.¹², m.p. 212°); yield, 1.1 g. (Found: C, 83.7; H, 5.0. $C_{20}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 83.9; H, 4.97%).

3-Phenyl-4-methyl-5:6-benzocoumarin: The solution of β -naphthol (2.88 g.) and α -acetylphenylacetonitrile (3.18 g.) in dry acetic acid (100 ml) was saturated with dry hydrochloric acid gas at room temperature (about three hours). Freshly fused zinc chloride (2.0 g.) was then added and dry hydrochloric acid gas was passed for next two hours at 50-60°. After three weeks the brown solution was diluted with water to about 750 ml.

9. Pascal and Normand, *Bull. Soc. Chim. (France)*, 1911, **9**, 1064.

10. Baker and Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, **127**, 1981.

11. Bargellini, Atli, *R. Acad. Lincei*, 1925, **2**, 261.

12. Cheema and Venkataraman, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 920.

and left overnight. Supernatant liquid was decanted off and the gummy mass deposited crystalline needles of 3-phenyl-4-methyl-5:6-benzocoumarin (1.4 g.) on boiling with alcohol (charcoal). This on two crystallisations from alcohol melted at 300°. (Found: C, 84.0; H, 5.0. $C_{20}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 83.9; H, 4.97%).

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
PATNA UNIVERSITY,
PATNA-5.

Received, March 31, 1967.